

The Nature and Properties of Black Light*

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Before discussing the new results of my research, I have the honor to inform the Academy that my experiments on the passage of ordinary light through opaque bodies have been repeated with full success by several observers, notably by Mr. Armaignac in Bordeaux and especially by Mr. H. Murat in Havre. The latter even succeeded, by following my instructions exactly, in obtaining results with black light superior to those achieved with Röntgen rays. Black light and rays of cathode origin are surely not similar radiations, as black light does not pass through substances like ebonite, which are completely transparent to Röntgen rays. Mr. Murat has sent me photographs of the interior of a fish's body, which I have the honor of presenting to the Academy. They show a dissection, layer by layer, which would be impossible to obtain with cathode rays, as I will explain shortly. The light from a simple lamp transformed into black light by the method I indicated, that is, by passing through metal plates, was sufficient to obtain these results.

In my first notes, I only wanted to publish the raw results of my experiments. They

seemed so inexplicable that it now seems necessary to explain the theories that led to their execution and that allowed us to anticipate them.

The goal I set myself was to explore the still unknown zone that separates the realm of light from that of electricity. I supposed, as I mentioned at the conclusion of my first note, that the forms of energy must be infinite in number. We only know a few, such as light, heat, and electricity. But these known forms must be connected by intermediate forms. These latter forms are still unknown simply because we do not have instruments capable of rendering them perceptible to our senses.

To discover one of these intermediate forms of energy, it was necessary to first find an instrument capable of detecting vibrations that are fewer in number than those of light and more numerous than those of electricity. Since photographic plates are sensitive to relatively few vibrations situated beyond the visible spectrum, it was to be hoped that they would also be sensitive to even fewer vibrations. If this was indeed the case, we would find ourselves in the intermediate zone between light and electricity. But then this new form of energy would have to possess some intermediate

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properties between those of light and those of electricity. It may no longer propagate like light and might propagate like electricity. In the latter case, the vibrations should not be stopped by opaque metallic bodies, regardless of their thickness. It is to verify these concepts that research has been pursued over the past two years. Without the theory that guided us, we would have stopped in the face of the failures that accompanied our first experiments.

The demonstration of the passage of light through thick metal plates was made quite quickly, but the results were accompanied by partial failures that caused me to delay their publication for a long time. Most often, the image was perfect on the outer edges of the plate or at its center, then suddenly stopped. Using several foreign metals could either facilitate or hinder the experiment. For instance, the presence of a polished tin foil behind the sensitive plate prevented light from passing through the aluminum plate covering the negative. Sometimes, equally satisfactory results were obtained by placing the glass in front of or behind the negative. Sometimes the image was negative, and sometimes it was positive. Clearly, electrical influences were at play, but the effects produced were undoubtedly due to the action of light, since, with all experimental conditions being equal, the images only formed when light fell on the opaque plates that blocked the frame.

I will explain in a forthcoming note how, using a new, infinitely sensitive instrument (a galvanometer with a moving coil in an intense magnetic field produced by a 30-volt, 2-ampere auxiliary current), I was able to demonstrate the release of electricity dur-

ing the formation of photographic images. For the moment, I only wish to present the experiments concerning the passage of ordinary light through opaque bodies and the transformations it undergoes.

In the following experiments, each photographic plate receives two sensitive glasses, one on its upper part and the other on its lower part.

One of these serves as a control, that is, it is intended to show, by being kept in the dark in the frame, that the image produced on the glass covering the second part of the plate only forms under the influence of black light. In this way, we entirely eliminate all hypotheses that might be made about the causes of image formation: stored light, pressure, heat, electricity, etc. Only the light that passed through the plate and was transformed into black rays produces the image, as no image is produced in the absence of this light.

The edges of the sensitive glass are covered with a double sheet of black paper, glued to the edges of the plate and folded behind the sensitive glass. The entire setup is placed in the dark inside the photographic frame with the metallic shutter plate through which the light must pass to impress the plate.

To eliminate from the outset the hypothesis of stored light, which photographers would undoubtedly propose, I attached a black paper cross to the back of the plate, which the light passing through the metal plates does not penetrate, except in the case of a prolonged exposure. As a result, it is reproduced in white on the photographic print. If the exposure time was too long, the cross would eventually be penetrated. I previously pointed out that black paper is only

opaque for short exposures. Ten sheets of black paper stacked over a plate and sensitive glass allow enough light to pass through to produce an excellent image after four hours of exposure to sunlight. The passage of light through the most opaque bodies, as I have already stated, is merely a matter of time.

Now I present a series of experiments that would seem quite contradictory if we did not have the theory I presented to explain them, and if we assumed that black light, like ordinary light, must propagate in a straight line.

With the frame being covered by one of the metals I mentioned—aluminum or iron, for example—one half of the metal plate is covered in turn by ten layers of black paper, which would be sufficient under the exposure conditions we use to stop the formation of the image on a sensitive plate. However, upon development, we find that the image is absolutely equal in intensity both under the part covered only by the metal and under the part where the metal is covered by ten layers of paper. If we place large iron discs several centimeters thick on this same metal plate, we find that these discs, despite their thickness, leave no trace on the image.

These experiments, which have been repeated in various ways, are fundamental. They first show us that the thickness of the opaque plates is irrelevant to the passage of light, just as it would be for the passage of electricity. These experiments also show that black light follows different laws of propagation than ordinary light. Indeed, if black light propagated in a straight line, the areas of the plate protected by the discs and the layers of paper placed over

the metal plates would be indicated by a shadow on the glass. But if black light obeys the laws of the propagation of electrical waves, it is enough for one point of the metal to receive rays for the rays to propagate across its entire surface.

Thus, light can be transformed into radiations that propagate like electrical currents. However, these are not electrical radiations, as ordinary electrical currents are not sufficient to produce the same effects. We are therefore in the presence of a mode of energy that is no longer light since it retains only a part of its properties and no longer obeys the laws of its propagation, and which is not electricity either, since known forms of electricity do not produce the same effects. Black light must therefore be considered a new force added to the small number of those we already know.